

APPROACHES TO SYNTHESIZING IMAGE PROCESSING PROGRAMS

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ABSTRACT

Machine learning techniques are examined as a means of automatically generating image processing programs. Non-structured techniques such as discovery systems and evolutionary processes are studied because they facilitate the exploration of enormous search spaces without a detailed knowledge base. The success of these methods depends on the algorithm representation and the effectiveness of performance evaluation. Mathematical morphology provides an algebraic representation which is powerful and challenging to program. The qualitative aspects of effective performance measures are also discussed.

INTRODUCTION

With processors becoming faster and more economical, it is now practical to use visual information in intelligent applications. Although these processors are able to execute operations at high speeds, the added processing power does not help determine *which* operations to perform. This is usually determined by an imaging expert whose task is to develop a sequence of operations which fulfills the visual requirements. Guided only by experience and intuition, he predicts which operations will lead to a successful solution. Several operations are applied; the results are viewed and mentally evaluated. Since many operations are usually required, the programmer must estimate how well subsequent operations will respond in light of the imposed goals. This process requires intensive effort to achieve acceptable results.

Because the primary bottleneck in constructing vision applications is software development, there is a strong motivation to automate this task. However, traditional techniques such as expert systems fail because the rule-base is unavailable. Automatic programming systems, such as [7], allow the expert to develop programs using high-level objectives; however, this task is nearly as difficult as programming with the image operations themselves. And, unless the rule-set is very large, the programmer will have difficulty expressing unique requirements.

Machine learning techniques have been used to generate small, morphological [8] programs for classifying binary

images. Gillies [1] used a genetic algorithm (GA) [2] to generate small, localized structuring elements (SEs). The SEs, which function like templates, must cooperate with a user-specified program-template - a *program form*. After training, the completed program produced nearly perfect classification on different handwritten scripts. The major accomplishment of this research is the successful integration of coarse-grain knowledge with fine-grain knowledge. The fine-grain knowledge, the unknown parameters, is developed by computer within the context of the user-specified coarse-grain knowledge, the program template. This is the appropriate division of labor since humans can easily describe macroscopic relationships and computers are well-suited to the tedious work of details.

The first attempt to synthesize *complete* morphological algorithms was done by Vogt [12]. This system accepts I/O pairs and generates an algorithm which produces the I/O mapping. The operator sequences are composed of a few different morphological operations and a small set of standard SEs. By design, this system is limited to finding morphological sequences of only one or two operation. Under these artificial constraints, the search space is limited to a manageable size. Vogt's later research argues that synthesizing longer sequences of morphological operations is dependent on performance criteria to guide the search. To date, effective performance measures do not exist [11].

Our previous research has focused on generating a collection of structuring elements to do classification of binary images [6]. This system operates in two phases. The first phase stochastically generates a large population of global structuring elements. The second phase uses a unique implementation of a genetic algorithm to find a set of SEs (i.e., features) which can be connected to a neural network to perform classification. The GA's goal is to force the features (i.e., SEs) to be as orthogonal as possible. Orthogonal features enable a simple neural network to be used as a classifier. In addition to grouping SEs into orthogonal sets, the second phase also makes modifications which minimize the size of the sets and simultaneously correct errors. After training, this system achieves high recognition rates on handwritten characters with very small sets of SEs.

Currently, we are conducting research which extends the previously mentioned work. First, we are working with grayscale images produced from typical CCD cameras. Secondly, we want to address the issues of constructing operations to perform specific tasks on these images. Similar to prior work, we will work with mathematical morphology as our imaging language. However, these transformations will be based on the grayscale extension of mathematical morphology [9].

AUTOMATIC PROGRAMMING SYSTEM

Image processing software is designed to do many different tasks (e.g., edge detection, noise removal, and feature enhancement). In our work, we address only one type of algorithm - *target acquisition* (TA). TA programs are used to identify the location of a specific class of objects in cluttered grayscale images. TA programs are essentially image-to-image transformations which process the images so that residues are placed at the locations of the targets. Figure 1 shows the operation of such a procedure, Ψ , with the target objects being rectangles.

Figure 1. Target Acquisition Algorithm.

We wish to automatically generate a suitable algorithm with minimal external input. Figure 2 illustrates a training set with the target objects manually delimited. Specifying the problem in this way allows the inference procedure to explore the space of algorithms in an unbiased manner. The

Figure 2. Generation of Target Acquisition Algorithm.

objective is to develop a sequence of operations which captures the essence of the targets without being specific to the training set.

In realistic situations, the number of potential algorithms is sufficiently large to preclude exhaustive search; therefore, techniques are needed to locate an acceptable solution without examining all possibilities. Researchers [10] believe that a system which achieves this goal must address three major issues. First, the algorithm representation must be rich enough to address the complex criteria found in images, yet also be amenable to search techniques. The system's designers must balance these opposing forces through judicious choice of representation. Secondly, the search techniques must be developed to exploit the properties of the representation. Lastly, performance measures must be incorporated into the search procedure to guide the synthesizing process. The performance measures, in part, must reflect the goals imposed by the user.

ALGORITHM REPRESENTATION

Mathematical morphology [8] is an approach to image processing which is rapidly gaining popularity. In contrast to approaches that work with symbolic structures, mathematical morphology works directly with individual pixels and their relationships to other pixels. Each morphological transformation probes the image for certain topological features while simultaneously removing extraneous information. Mathematical morphology is especially appropriate for the TA process since location information is maintained through each transformation.

A single morphological transformation changes an image in very primitive ways; however, by assembling the appropriate operations in the proper sequence, the underlying image structure is gradually revealed. As an example, Algo-

rithm 1 defines a morphological algorithm which was manually designed to locate computer monitors in a laboratory scene. (In order to avoid the difficulties of presenting the syntax of mathematical morphology, the pseudo code is shown instead.)

1. Threshold the image at graylevels 100 and 255
2. Dilate result of step 1 with a CYLINDER of size 30
3. Complement result of step 2
4. Take result of step 3 and threshold at 255 (make binary)
5. Dilate result of step 4 with CYLINDER of size 20
6. Complement result of step 5
7. Erode result of step 6 with a RING of size 50
8. Take intersection of results 5 and 7

Algorithm 1. Pseudo-code for morphological algorithm.

Figure 3 shows the results of applying this algorithm to three different laboratory scenes. In this figure, the left-hand image is the input scene and the right-hand image is the result of the transformation. In each case, the output image contains residues which correspond to the correct location of the computer screens.

Although not obvious from the individual instructions, the goal of this algorithm is to locate large, dark regions surrounded by a thin white strip of light pixels. Notice that the "surrounded" is essential; locating only just the large dark regions or thin white strips leads to numerous false alarms. The non-intuitive nature of Algorithm 1 reinforces the desire to automate this process.

The exact definition of each operation is beyond the scope of this paper. The important thing to notice is that the power of the morphological operations comes from the parameters CYLINDER and RING. These parameters, SEs, are fixed images with many different shapes and sizes available. (In the case of CYLINDER and RING, the shapes are derived from their symbolic name). The large number of shape-size-operator combinations adds to the already exponential search space. Fortunately, the morphological transformations obey several mathematical properties which enable the effects of the operations to be predicted. In general, a small change in the SE will result in a correspondingly small change in function. Gradualistic behavior such as this greatly increases the chances of finding the proper SE without examining all size-shape combinations.

SEARCH STRATEGIES

Finding an acceptable program solution requires searching through the enormous space of all possible algorithms. Because a systematic exploration of this space will fail due to the enormous size of the problem, non-structured techniques in machine learning are needed to search this space. Non-structured techniques enable such problems to be addressed without specifying a set of production rules.

For example, genetic algorithms gather characterizing information through quasi-random exploration. Expansive exploration enables many diverse algorithms to be sampled without committing too many resources to any particular region of the search space. During the sampling process, operator sequences which only partially solve the problem will be examined. If it can be determined that an operator sequence's function is nearly acceptable, it is likely that an additional operator or change in parameter will bring it even closer to a solution.

Algorithm 2 is a very simple control structure which embodies the philosophy of discovery systems [4] and [3]. A priority queue contains a set of partially developed operator sequences. At each cycle, the best candidate, cand, is given an opportunity to prove itself as a possible solution. For each candidate, an operation is selected as a plausible extension. (For morphological operations, an operation consists of a transformation-SE pair.) The operator is applied to cand and the result is evaluated based on whether beneficial changes have been made in the images. In general, evaluation will be based on the difference between the function of the extended operator sequence and the desired function. The best operator sequences are inserted into the queue and the process repeats.

```

Initialize queue with the identity transformation
REPEAT
  cand := Head(queue);
  op := Select Operation;
  result := op(cand);
  IF (Evaluate(cand, result, goal) is promising) THEN
    Insert(op(cand), queue);
UNTIL solved;

```

Algorithm 2. Search Process.

Often, a problem is best solved by decomposing the problem into sub-problems. Once the smaller problems are solved, the original problem is resolved by combining the solutions to the sub-problems with logic operations. The required generality is obtained by stochastically combining partial solutions with the available logic operations. At random intervals, two sequences are combined with union or intersection. Similar to natural selection, the best performers are more likely to be selected for mixing. In this fashion, new material is constantly being introduced to the population of algorithms. Other applications have used similar evolutionary strategies with good results [5].

PERFORMANCE MEASURES

Stochastic search methods require that the promising portions of the search space be recognized; likewise, poor regions of the search space must also be identified. Accu-

Figure 3. Application of Morphological Algorithm.

rately labeling the states of the search space permits the search effort to be directed towards the most favorable regions. Since incomplete algorithms are necessary components of larger algorithms, the performance measure must *predict* how these small program stubs will perform with additional modification. Evaluation is particularly difficult in the early stages of the search because small, undeveloped algorithms transform the images in very primitive ways. This type of behavior may necessitate performance measures which change according to the progress of the search.

In terms of target acquisition, a good operator will simultaneously enhance the features of the target regions and remove extraneous information from non-target regions. Determining whether images are transformed in a beneficial manner is accomplished by taking a series of measurements on the target regions and non-target regions. Large differences between these two values indicate the newest transformation has further discriminated the target from the non-target regions. Of course, whether a future operation will ultimately address this difference depends on whether the measure of evaluation is effective.

Performance measures have received very little attention in the research community. Consequently, the nature of the measures and how they should be integrated into the search process is still an open question. Intuitively, a performance measure should incorporate several qualitative properties. It should be:

1. Goal-Driven
2. Predictive
3. Consistent

The first point simply ensures that the user-imposed constraints are taken into consideration; certain regions of the images are of particular importance and should be examined carefully. The second point indicates that differences between target and non-target regions should be established. Favoring these tendencies will enable future operations to key on these differences. Finally, it is important for the transformation's effects to be consistently observed on all images.

DISCUSSION

Automatically generating image processing software is an application which is considered appropriate for non-structured, machine learning techniques. Non-structured methods differ from conventional approaches which are often founded on a rule-base. In the domain of developing image processing software, it is extremely difficult to formulate a good set of rules.

In order to facilitate this research, it is desirable to organize the system so that the major sub-systems are relatively independent of each other. By using an image-to-image transformation language such as mathematical morphology, the search procedure can treat the individual opera-

tions as abstract functions. Isolating the search procedure from the specific algorithm representation allows different representations to be explored without extensive changes to the search process. The evaluation function is also unaware of the nature of the transformations; evaluation is done according to the input image, transformation result, and goal state. The different types of encapsulation allow for the possibility that any of the three major components can be used in entirely new environments.

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